

**DISASTER CAPITALISM AND THE COMING ANARCHY: WHAT POLICY OPTION
FOR AFRICA- HIBERNATING OR REBOOTING?**

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DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.10516504

Abstract

Surprisingly the gap between the left and the right is about to close as there is consensus about the coming anarchy spiraling paradoxically from the weakest link of global capitalism- Africa. The cause of the coming anarchy varies between left and right: for rightists, championed by Kaplan and Fukuyama whose works intensify these arguments, state failure expressed in political decay will degenerate into rent governance from depleting resources and exploding population in Africa, leading to resources competition, crisis and anarchy. For the left, the coming anarchy though came from state failure but organically originated from unequal relations intensified by unfettered capitalism expressed through the shock doctrine. The outcome of the coming anarchy is disaster capitalism outraged to consume global capitalism through the instrument of creative destruction. Africa is currently faced with two alternative policy options: hibernation or rebootism. The paper recommended rebootism with six policy outlines to reverse the coming anarchy and reconstruct Africa's evolution to maturity or development.

Keywords: Creative destruction, disaster capitalism, globalization, shock doctrine, the coming anarchy.

1. Introduction

The obsession of Fukuyama's 'The End of History and the Last Man' demonstrates the dominance of liberal democracy and unfettered capitalism (capitalist democracy) as an inevitable

international doctrine (Fukuyama 1992) which when intensified under globalization, correlates into contradictions (Ake 1981, Amin 1976:74) that produces Kaplan's 'the coming anarchy'.

Globalizing liberal democracy and neoliberal economy with hegemonic determinism reproduce and reinforce order and wealth in the global North and perpetuate disaster and miserable poverty in the global South.

Conteh-Morgan (2006) reflected the paradoxical nature and character of globalization:

Globalization as a system, a discourse, a process, and even an ideology is made up of several fundamental characteristics, such as: (1) the undisputed dominance and infallibility of the market because it offers freedom of choice for the consumer, and is the arena for free trade, competition, investment, and production, among others; (2) the subordination of the state and public interests to private interests manifested in extensive privatization and the steady disappearance of the social welfare state; (3) intense competition among companies which results not only in mergers and conglomerates, but in corporate downsizing, massive lay-offs of ordinary workers, wage decreases, elimination of social benefits, and even pensions; (4) the commodification of everything from culture, education and information, to air, water, and other common goods, all subject to appropriation by the most efficient companies for better management and increased growth; and (5) the conviction that the planet's resources are infinite and inexhaustible, accordingly, the solution to the problems of unemployment, poverty, hunger, and the like, should be infinite growth. The consequence of these dogmas of neoliberal internationalism is gross inequality and increasing human insecurity in income, food, health, community, and the like.

Africa is a battered continent, from slavery to balkanization, to colonialism and currently neo-liberalism. At what stage should Africa be integrated into what is beyond her evolutionary¹ capability?

Globalization prevents developing and poor states in the global South from being responsive to the needs of its citizens who are critically helpless and distanced from the economy. Global indicators have not pictured Africa favorably in the context of international politics (power relations), global economy (resource capacity and utilization), or historical narratives (cultural

¹ This paper adopted evolutionary theory or Life cycle theory to explain different stages of life of a state. Every organism as with state, evolve from ^aBirth to ^bGrowth to ^cMaturity (developed) and ^dDeath (Decay). Intense competition under globalization and capitalism between or among states at different stages of evolution produces unequal relation and reinforces exploitation through induced shock leading to state failure. When weak state fails, the creative destruction is release to diminish the value created by the strong.

evaluation). Zambakari (2012) expressed that ‘when assessing key economic, social and political indicators in Africa, the last fifty years signaled general disappointment’. Africa is the current challenge and admissibly the new experiment on development prescriptions of any sort. (Stone 2014; Rotberg 2002, 2004; Moss 2007:7) Africa has become a global laboratory for crisis and state failure.

The United Nations (UN DESA report 2015) captured the fate of Africa in frightening statistics while predicting global future trends. The report projected that the global population will hit 9.7 billion in 2050 and 11.2 billion in 2100; half of the expected population growth will come from Africa- essentially from Nigeria, Congo, Ethiopia, Tanzania, and Uganda. The report identified Africa’s challenge with a double population growth of 28 African countries in 2100. The concentration of population growth in poor countries presents its challenge.

Kaplan (2000) in the same vein predicted that Africa's population is doubling and exploding without caution with diseases and poverty persisting and increasing as natural resources continue to deplete. He identified rural migration surge to shantytowns (where jobless youths- with ethnic and religious consciousness- proliferate without social facilities and government presence) cluttering large cities and wreaking havoc at night; a clear picture of Lewis’s dualism where poverty and traditional sector intersect with wealth and modernity (United Nation Chronicle 2008).

Capitalism as a culprit creates (city) illiberal democracy (Zakaria 1997) in Africa and depopulates rural enclave societies to migrate toward their urban center that cannot accommodate new entrees.

Growing population with failing states and laden bureaucracies habiting the world's largest poor people, growing shantytowns, uncontrolled violence, massive degradation, environmental

scarcity, cultural and racial clashes, geographical density, and transformation of war across broken borders put Africa under intense pressure. (Kaplan 2000)

If we take Fukuyama seriously and capture the other half of his book title- 'The Last Man'; this will genuinely be Milton Friedman's advocate of neoliberalism order. Africa has defaulted critically on the neoliberal doctrine as the weakest link in the capitalist value chain and with reprimand consequences.

By implication, Africa's population is rising and with the intensification of global capitalism by 2050, the main source of income for African countries will be rent from extractive mineral resources that feed the voracious elites exclusively and from mere subsistence agriculture that are often afflicted by price distortions in the global market.

Agricultural yields in the continent are low because of poor technology, crude implement usage, low seed-yielding varieties, degradation of soil quality arising from over-farming and pollution, poor storage facilities and practices, lack of or weak infrastructure to support the sector activities, absence of processing technology and facilities, poor and inconsistent agriculture policies, high dubious double interest rate lending regime, communal disputes/war on farmland ownership - cumulatively accounts for food shortage, food insecurity and massive food importation to the African continent.

By 2050 with the expected population rise, there will be intense food insecurity in Africa. Health, education, and infrastructural investment in Africa are lacking to support production. The public sector in Africa is still largely patrimonial and overshadows the weak craving private sector in investment and employment. A huge gap exists in employment for both skilled and unskilled labour to support internal production.

The logic of the population prediction is that the population tends to shrink with modernity (maturity stage) and increase with primitivism, stagnation, or orthodoxy (birth or early growth stage). Production and living conditions will rise and fall respectively.

Conservatively, living conditions in Africa will retrogress or decline by half, and resource scarcity will intensify resource competition and organically lead to the inevitable decay of the state arising from conflict of resource utilization. The crisis will degenerate from one state to another with the capacity to persist in scale and intensity in the absence of leadership.

The summation of Fukuyama's 'End of History and the Last Man', The United Nations DESA Report 2015 on population growth, and Kaplan's 'The Coming Anarchy' typifies Africa as the blueprint of anarchy in the international capitalist system. Anarchy is the displacement of order caused by state weakness or failure and the absence of strong institutions to regulate state and market behaviour.

The paper is divided into six sections; Section 1: Introduction (Evaluate Africa's dilemma); Section 2: Conceptual Framework; Section 3: Captures Africa in the shock doctrine complex; Section 4: Examine the fate of Africa and seeks options open to Africa to liberate itself; Section 5: Made six policy recommendations to evade the coming Anarchy and Section 6 concludes the paper.

2. Conceptual Framework

Creative Destruction: A condition where intense competitive innovations frequently reallocate resources to efficient producers from their rivals with high transaction costs spiraling into market failure and disappearing market. Under capitalism, with the rapidity of competitive innovations, new products are frequently introduced into the market that make older products obsolete

(preventing investment recovery and increasing transaction cost) which introduces shock, instability, or chaos to the market and state. The exploitative nature of capitalism creates incentives for the exploited to provide alternative innovation from being alienated and the circle continues to reproduce chaos and anarchy unregulated in the long run.

Disaster Capitalism: Disaster capitalism serves as a neoliberal instrument that permits the construction of unregulated markets to exploit opportunities in vulnerable societies or states that are experiencing shocks or natural disasters. Once shock, chaos, or disaster is experienced in a state or society, the government deployment of unregulated capitalist policies that lack populist support to redistribute wealth (as a template for creating efficiency rather than equality) with the consequence being to cause replacement or displacement effects. The practice (by capitalist organization or cooperation) of making profits out of misery using public policy.

Globalization: The internationalization of unregulated capitalism and restrictive state in the organization and affairs of the market.

Shock Doctrine: The express manifestation of using state policies to promote the reallocation of resources that seek to deepen inequalities. Capitalism inevitably creates disaster as a means to reap huge profits for corporations or powerful enterprises.

The Coming Anarchy: Anarchy is the displacement of order caused by state weakness or failure and the absence of strong institutions to regulate market behaviour. Kaplan depicts the coming anarchy as a reflection of a failing institutional framework in weak states that has global economic consequences.

3. Capturing Africa in the shock doctrine complex

Naomi Klein's book, 'Shock Doctrine- The Rise of Disaster Capitalism' comes in handy to demonstrate the consequence both for Africa and the world expressing closely the "butterfly effect" or "the domino" on a global system. The immoral foundation upon which global capitalism is built- exploitation- makes a producer nation's policy draconian to consumption countries. Western toxic capital, mass production, and unfair and unequal trade policies impact Africa making Africa unfit for the comparative advantage debate and practice. Western toxic capital tends to locate its investment vastly in disaster or vulnerable environments where it can reap massive gains from the misfortune of its host.

Klein (2006:485) explains shock doctrine as 'any strategy based on exploiting the window of opportunity opened by a traumatic shock and relies heavily on the element of surprise or a state of shock in a moment when there is a gap between fast-moving events (a crisis condition created by capitalist failure) and the information (accurate policy responses) that exists to explain them.

Unfettered capitalism strongly advocates for a rollback, restrained, contained, or lean state that is concretely disengaged (social welfare) through privatization or deregulation in the affairs of the market or economy. When market failure occurs with its shocks (recession occurs at least once in every decade), a lean state is inevitably disabled or disempowered to respond to citizen's democratic expectations. Market failure therefore puts a lean state's response abysmally in a weak posture to deal with shocks.

Capitalism creates disaster by promoting and propagating competition between unequal - North and South; as resource competition intensifies over resource scarcity, African leaders (under a lean state profile) will lack innovation to reconfigure the complex institutions necessary to stabilize the continent. African leaders will rather sort for easy alternatives of window-shopping for foreign investors and Western capital. Since investing in Africa will be risky in unstable

societies- with a high likelihood of instability, investors will crowd in on the vulnerability of Africa on a short-term basis with the inherent motive to reap massive profit from the host and venture on capital flight.

The conviction to repatriate capital to another safe and stable environment hinges on the inability of the vulnerable host to evolve a state or continental policy direction from which investors will retain their confidence to sustain their investment. Investors therefore window-shop for irresistible opportunities from vulnerable environments they cannot get elsewhere principally on a short-run basis. Investors are guided principally by knowledge and perception of the host policy whether they are stable/accommodating to business and profit or not.

When investment is uncertain and unstable job security tends to collapse with the magnitude of unpredictability, capturing the resource scarcity and resource competition in the equation, the displacement effect will intensify and more jobs will be lost or frozen out from the private sector towards the public sector that is unable to manage the economy. Ironically, a lean fragile state with frightening privatization failures will be unable to respond to crisis.

High privatization failure was evident in Asia, Latin America, and Africa during the Structural Adjustment Programme in the 1980s. Expectedly, the public sector will rationalize (by reducing recurrent expenditures like diabetic patients cutting off excess sugar in a bit to survive) because of deficit capital and insufficient investment. Unemployment rise associated with high inflationary pressure produces the misery index, thus misery across Africa will rise above average for the population, conservatively at 50%. *The number of miserable people* in Africa in 2050 will be more than 1 billion people; which is a sufficient condition/incentive to spur anarchy as witnessed in the Arab spring commencing from North Africa.

Shantytowns and poverty will proliferate Africa's major cities and intersect at a point where the inequality between the wealthy cities (dominated by few rich elites and vanishing middle class) and the shanty poor reflect with reality (of failing state and weak private sector) and the dynamism will spark up anarchy that will collapse states and the source of the conflict-capitalism. Consequently, anarchy will wither states in Africa and hunt global capitalism through the logic of creative destruction -

Capitalism necessarily produces seeds of its destruction through the accommodation or accumulation of inherent conflicting conditions that promote competition between classes, firms, or individuals to repeatedly seek change through innovations that are hardly consolidated. Competition rather than cooperation offsets the needed social equilibrium and in its place produces frequent displacement leading to instability and anarchy.

4. The fate of Africa – what options for Africa to liberate itself?

The African continent (residing in the Southern poor hemisphere) is no doubt faced with a developmental crisis that threatens its evolutionary process, being currently at its growth stage of development and is placed in a sprint race with the developed rich countries of the North hemisphere at maturity. The currency of globalization is competition, can Africa survive unfettered capitalism under Western hegemony at its evolutionary growth stage? What option for Africa to liberate itself? Hibernation or Rebootism?

Hibernation is a state of sleep, inaction, or inactivity. Currently, Africa's woes expose that the continent is experiencing a nightmare (occurring in a traumatized sleep). Garba (2003) acknowledged this fact by asking who is thinking for Africa. Who is benefiting from the neoliberal advice that is inflicting shock on Africa(ns)? Who are the losers? When will Africa awake?

Garba (2003) gave significant insight to demonstrate Africa's past, present, and possible future and how state failure was established by adopting Western theories and models for Africa's development.

Table 1. Western Ideas, Primary Beneficiaries, and Main Losers

Western Ideas	Effects in Africa, Asia, and Europe	Primary Beneficiaries	Main Losers
Gap models, growth theories, and vicious cycle models (from the 1950s)	External imbalance in primary exporting and net foreign borrows.	Western businesses, consumers, governments, intellectuals, and multilateral organizations.	Rural population and the urban poor.
Monetarism (1979-82)	The external debt crisis of 1982	Western businesses, consumers, governments, intellectuals, and	Rural population and the urban poor.

		multilateral organizations	
Washington Consensus (1980s)	Economic decline in most non-western countries (in Africa, East Europe, Central and South Asia, etc.	Western businesses, consumers, governments, intellectuals, and multilateral organizations.	The rural population, the urban poor, and middle class
Capital account liberalization (1990s)	The Asian crisis of 1997 and spillovers	Western businesses, consumers, governments, intellectuals, and multilateral organizations	Labour, consumers, businesses, and some rulers in Indonesia, the Philippines, South Korea, etc

Adapted from Garba (2003), The past, present and possible futures of Africa

Africa must wake up from its slumber and ignore the loser’s paradigm that has been fostered in Africa in the past by Western thinkers. Neoliberal theories are deepening Africa into a crisis of underdevelopment because they serve solely the interest of the Western world. The hibernating option of waiting for others to resolve Africa’s problems has inflicted traumatic shock and Kaplan’s ‘The Coming Anarchy’ is a modern realist interpretation of the outcome of Africa’s future. Hibernation is essentially a platform for incremental renovation of existing structures.

We are at this point only left with rebootism. A condition of destroying the vestige of the past and reconstructing a new future that is extensively internalized to consolidate growth and nurture conditions for development. Africa has been backstabbed (during colonialism and in the neoliberal post-colonial era) in the past and if she must make progress, she must engage the continent in self-discovery of what Africa wants the future to reflect. Africa must begin to reconstruct its consciousness of how to internally mobilize the continent towards pan-African development.

Africa must reconstruct its leadership role in this process and harness the power of cooperating with its huge population and energy to rebuild Africa. Africa must define her purpose; and rediscover her path towards her desired destination. Africa is the home of human civilization. Africa must begin to reconstruct a new beginning for her future generation that is sustainable. A

framework that directs Africa's energy toward liberating Africa. Rebootism set a new platform to reorder a crumbling past and provide the opportunity for innovation to drive sustainable development.

5. Recommendations

Africa can redirect its history from Western predation using six cardinal points

1. Statecraft

Africa herself is essentially a bigger part of her problem. Every organism that is infected carries within itself, the immunity to heal itself. Africa is bedeviled with a leadership crisis that is uncommitted to democratic, transparent, accountable governance and development. To reverse this misfortune, Africa must look inward and reconstruct leadership based on purpose and achievement. African states and their leadership must be committed to defining a development paradigm that is sincere toward the collective interest of all Africans.

Statecraft- the science and art of governance must be the cornerstone of reconstructing leadership in Africa. The capacity of leadership essentially in governance must be raised above the current trend and giving serious concern with the required educational capacity to deal with the complexities of the challenges facing the states/continent. An institutional framework must be constructed to function adequately to restrain the rent-seeking behavior of African leaders to enable the continent to invest in its people and future (create institution-driven leadership).

2. Invest in human capacity and technology

Africa as a continent must drive its development. It must through its peer review mechanism develop a realistic template to advise and challenge Africa's leaders to massively invest in the development of human capacity and technology.

The enhancement of the human capacity to develop indigenous technology to meet its cultural challenges must be given major priority. The volatility of mineral resources in the hands of global capitalism is very glaring. Soft power- human resources development is now the priced factor in international commerce. African leaders and the continent must invest a huge part of its resources in recreating and sustaining itself through human capital development that is capable of driving its development internally.

3. Socioeconomic integration

African economies are disarticulated within the African continent (Ake 1981). It is rather integrated into the global capitalist economy with huge dependency on the continent draining its resources and restraining its capacity to self-develop. There is low patronage and interaction among Africa's economies- commerce and tourism. Capital outflow from Africa to other continents is massive and detrimental to Africa's survival. The craving for Western brands amidst scarce resources bites Africa's economy negatively. Africa must produce and consume what is produced in Africa if Africa must survive. Garba (2003) rated 'current economic relations between Africa and the rest of the world as significant and asymmetrical (especially with high-income countries) and intra-Africa economic relations as relatively insignificant'.

Table 2. Current condition of economic relations between Africa and different regions.

Africa ^a		Asia ^b	Eastern Europe and Central Asia	Rest of Europe	Middle East	Americas
Africa	Insignificant	Significant and strongly Asymmetrical	Not Significant and asymmetrical	Very significant and strongly asymmetrical	Insignificant	Very significant and strongly asymmetrical

Adopted from Garba (2003), The past, present and possible futures of Africa.

Note:

- a. Mainly informal and with countries sharing borders or in the same region.
- b. Mainly Japan, Asia Tigers, Taiwan, China and India.
- c. Mainly France, Great Britain, Belgium, Spain, Netherlands and Nordic countries.
- d. Mainly the United States and Canada.

African states must integrate socioeconomic relations intensify free trade zones and freeze taxes as incentives to encourage Afroeconomics (African economic relations). Africa should facilitate a monetary zone (in fashion like the European Union) with a single currency. This will step up the capacity of Africa to negotiate with the rest of the world on terms favorable to African states and their people. Africa should then use this platform to organize trade discourse with the European Union on its Economic Partnership Agreement (EPA) and America on its Africa Growth Opportunity Act (AGOA). Africa as an economic bloc can reverse the shock doctrine complex on her economy by engaging in economic diplomacy.

4. Lessons from China and India

Two giants of the Asia continent with half of the world's population have defeated the warning of Malthus's theory of population and its effect on the economy. Firstly, China and India have demonstrated that population can be an advantageous resource if it is invested in to gain economic strength. China and India are markets in their domain. Capturing the benefits of the internal market is possible if there is capacity to sustain it.

Secondly, China and India have deployed technology as a tool to capture the gains of global capitalism for their market; both countries are self-sustaining and utilizing the price mechanism against advanced economies. Africa can take this path to development.

5. Lessons from Europe's History

Three periods are significant in European history that can serve as a recipe for Africa's development.

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The first is the Dark Age period (490- 967AD), the second is the Enlightenment period (1650-1789AD) and the third is the Industrial Revolution (1760-1914).

<http://www.worldology.com/Europe>

The Dark Age was characterized by warfare driven by religious extremism, superstitious belief systems, and political absolutism. It was a period of great unrest and instability among Empires and emerging Kingdoms across Europe. It was a formative age with great destruction and death. African states still exhibit a large dose of instability and political absolutism serving as deficit constraining nation building.

The Enlightenment (intellectual) period witnessed the developments in Western philosophy and scientific and academic understanding. It was the age of reasoning, pragmatism, human liberty, and the development of the legal system to regulate behaviour. It provided the knowledge, attitude, and institutions that established the Industrial Revolution. Mokyr (2007) expressed that the Enlightenment provided the agenda, capabilities, selection, and diffusion of ideas for European growth and development.

The Industrial Revolution symbolizes the refinement and manifestation of the conversion of the ideas of the Enlightenment into technologies and the application of the same for industrial purposes or usage. It was the age of invention, mass production, and the birth of capitalism.

The European Enlightenment preceded the industrial revolution and both are intertwined profoundly (Heilbron 2003).

Europe came out of the dark age through an intellectual scientific revolution where scholarship in all areas of human endeavors was encouraged and honored. From the intellectual revolution, Europe gathered the resources and tools needed to launch into the industrial revolution that set

Europe apart. From this process, Europe has sustained and integrated its culture and economy into a dominant global culture and economy. African leaders currently encourage violence over scholarship, a character associated with the European Dark Age period. Africa cannot build a future with violence.

Africa is home to humanity, the gene of Africa is not inferior to other continents, development can be replicated; scholarship- research, and development (R&D) can drive Africa's sustainability and see the world from the prism of Africa's challenge. Africa can change the global narrative of the continent as home to poverty and underdevelopment. The future can begin today with the collective commitment of Africans to develop the continent.

6. Africa must develop a sustainable and realist population policy.

Africa's current burden is heavy on governance and leads to economic dysfunction. It is becoming difficult to plan adequately for a rising and upscale population that is difficult to predict. Africa must pull her resources towards a realistic population policy so that she can adequately provide education, health, and other essential infrastructure. The demographical structure of Africa's population must be known and advanced with incentives to erase the conditions that degenerate the continent into crises and anarchy. With the right policy driven towards capturing the real size of the population, African States can freeze out the continent's most critical challenge- poverty. Africa can with a known population, eliminate poverty and empower the people, the continent's most valuable resources. The states and continents must develop a database on their demography to guide and support policy direction for development.

6. Conclusion

Kaplan's warning of the coming anarchy in Africa is timely. It brings to the fore the vexatious issue of state failure and the consequence of neglecting the human element in development. Unchecked population growth is still a threat to the quality of life in modern times in correlation to the available resources. Once the institutions of governance evade its usefulness, anarchy overrides all other interests.

Fukuyama and the neoliberalism movement connect the discourse on the political and economic spectrum; objectifying Western ideological footage under globalization by setting capitalist democracy as the inevitable end of human history.

The Fukuyama, Kaplan, and other neoliberals situate the superstructure of society and the crisis of the state in Africa to be a function of political decay (Fukuyama 2011:14) and thus Africa is required to follow the footprint of Western mentors, a new re-civilization order.

Essentially, Kaplan's "the coming anarchy" emanates from the failing institutional structure of governance arising from the rentier state paradigm and resource curse syndrome. Kaplan saw Africa's inevitable collapse from the coming anarchy owing to changing environmental challenges and population exploitation; with both interfaces, African state resources will deplete leading to resource scarcity, resource competition, and then anarchy. Kaplan's analysis of the coming anarchy is partial and incomplete.

A holistic analytical framework captures the emerging conditions of Kaplan's 'The Coming Anarchy' and Marx, Engel, and Lenin's 'Withering of the State'; the collective equation points to the intensity of the parasitic nature of capitalist exploitation built into the (international) social relations of production that creates alienation and inequality, poverty, revolution and freedom of the oppressed.

The capitalization of the globe with the Western introduction of the shock doctrine complex coaxed premature states to fail and advance neoliberalism as global' social relations of production network and movement which has consequences for the global system.

Klein (2007) stressed that the shock doctrine of the Milton Friedman movement caused the state to compulsorily fail in Latin America, Asia, and Africa in the 1970s and 1980s (especially during the Structural Adjustment Programme) witnessed in the South. Thus, 'the end of history and the last man' in addition to 'the coming anarchy', draws Schumpeter's (1975: 82-85) creative destruction or Amin's (2011) 'the destructive dimensions of accumulation' as a self-fulfilling prophecy against capitalist democracy and globalization, an order built on inequality and exploitation of the weak. Reversing the effect of disaster capitalism and the coming anarchy will mean eliminating the voracious and vociferous conditions leading to the crisis of capitalism or redeeming humanity from capitalism.

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SAU-journal of Management and Social Science, Volume 1, No.2.

Cite as

Ifaka. J. O (2016). Disaster capitalism and the coming anarchy: What policy option for Africa-
Hibernating or rebooting? SAU-journal of Management and Social Science, Volume 1, No.2.